

SOIL SALINITY IN INDIA: A REVIEW OF CAUSES, EFFECTS AND RESTORATION MEASURES

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Abstract

In recent years, salinization of soil is one of the challenging environmental concerns occurring all over the world. The effects of concentration of salt can be detected in both natural (primary) as well as man-made (secondary) environment. This is due to massive urbanization and industrialization in coastal regions, Soil salinity may lead to degradative changes in the composition of natural water resources, loss of fertile soil, loss of biodiversity, changes in local climatic conditions which in turn affects many aspects like, increasing salinization (salt affected soil) of lands converted in to non-productive conditions which significantly affects human life and posing major interruption to the economic development of farmers and their economy in the country. Furthermore, the overview of salinization and its effects on ecology, agriculture and economic growth and development is presented in this paper. Purpose of this review paper represented is according to most recent literature and refines knowledge on consistent research efforts for the types of soil salinity, problems of soil salinization, effect on plant growth and management strategies in agriculture to mitigate soil conditions in the salinity affected areas as well as rise in crop productivity and suggests future perspectives for on-going salinity research in the country.

Key words: - Salinization, Soil Salinity, Salt Tolerance, Sustainable Agriculture Environment, Agricultural Productivity, Economic Development, Ecological Functions

Introduction:

In India around 18% of the world's human population and 15% of the world's livestock population on merely 2.4% of the world's geographical area (Bhattacharya et al., 2015). Population growth in India has shown increasing trend with food production. Since independence, India has made significant success in agriculture sector. In spite of the technological modernizations in agriculture, this dramatically increased food production in the past few years, scares food insecurity triggers globally is being challenged by several environmental factors such as climate change (Parry et al., 1999; Rosenzweig et al., 2004; Godfray et al., 2010), diversion of arable lands for biofuel production and environmental degradation (Oldeman 1998; Pimentel, 2006; Escobar et al., 2009), intensive cropping, deforestation and biodiversity loss (Foley et al., 2005; Tschardt et al., 2012), fresh water security (Lotze-Campen et al., 2008), increased population, urbanization and food wastage etc. (Parfitt et al., 2010; Pardeep kumar et al., 2020). The rising realization that climate change would poorly affect global food production of the majority of developing countries (Godfray et al., 2010).

In general, many unwanted anthropogenic activities have caused severe harm to agro-ecosystem health, carbon and hydrological cycle and flora-fauna diversity which are vital to a sustainable future (Foley et al., 2005). In the recent trends, the competition for land use from housing, bio-energy and industrial sectors linked with severe water shortages and the alarming rate of natural resource degradation and biodiversity loss (FAO, 2011) which have necessitated a paradigm shift in the conventional ways and mean of food production. The goals of higher food requirements due to demographic, economic and trade liberalization are exerting heavy pressures on India's limited land and water resources.

The salinity issue is becoming more serious challenge in sustainable environment for food and nutritional security in the developing countries. A wide range of research articles are documented against soil salinity. Salinization of terrestrial and aquatic environment both are a significantly rising global problem in the last few years. Worldwide, approx. 950 million hector (ha) of land are estimated to be salt affected, with salinity affecting 23% of arable land (Szabolcs, 1985; Szabolcs, 1990). Globally saline soil hotspots include Argentina, China, India, Pakistan, Sudan, United States and many countries in Central and Western Asia (Aquist et al., 2016; Ghassemi et al., 1995), while as such the country India has a vast area under coastal agro-ecosystem with very low productivity, which is inhibited by the poorest farming (G. Gururaja Rao et al., 2019). Designing for the effective and sustainable development of this ecosystem requires adoption of integrated approach to soil and water practices and

necessary measures to conserve the ecology. The major issues detected in coastal soils are: 1) Influence of tidal waves and periodical inundation by tidal water 2) Shallow water table enriched with salt to increase in soil salinity during winter and summer months 3) Heavy rainfall 4) poor surface and subsurface drainage condition 5) lack of irrigation water and acute salinity and 6) poor socioeconomic conditions of the farming community for using high investment technologies.

Soil salinity and its salinization:

An index of the concentration of salts occurs in soil is known as soil salinity which is usually expressed as electrical conductivity (EC). The process of buildup of salt concentration in soil is known as soil salinization. Such a level of salinization impacts on the agriculture production, environmental health, economics and quality of life. It involves a combination of processes like evaporation, salt precipitation and dissolution, salt transport and ion-exchange.

Salinity is a term that includes saline, sodic and alkaline soils (van Beek and Tóth, 2012), respectively defined as (a) higher salt concentration, (b) higher sodium cation (Na^+) concentration, and (c) higher pH, often due to high CO_3^{2-} concentration, in the soil. Soil salinization leads to the change or even interference of the natural biological (Smith et al., 2015), biochemical (Decock et al., 2015), hydrological (Keesstra et al., 2012) and erosional (Berendse et al., 2015) Earth Cycles. In India, degradation of land due to soil erosion affects over 40% (150 m ha) of the total geographical area (Dabral et al., 2008). High salinization stages can thus result to the loss of the emerging resources, goods and services of soil which is impacting agricultural production and environmental health (Rengasamy, 2006), eventually evolving into a sociocultural and human health issue (Brevik et al., 2015) that obstructs economic and general welfare.

Primary Salinization: (Natural process in salinization of soil):

Natural salinization is the development of salts due to geological, hydrological and pedological processes. It includes physical and chemical weathering of rock materials or sediments with high salt content. Salts are released and made soluble and transported away from their source of origin through surface or groundwater streams. The salts brought down from the upstream by rivers to the plains and their deposition along with alluvial materials and weathering of rocks. In arid regions, the concentration of salts gradually increases until they start precipitating in soil due to limited natural precipitation and percolation, high vaporization and transpiration rates. In low lying areas with high groundwater table and locked topography which favors soil salinization. The fossil salt deposits (e.g., marine deposits) are also responsible for salinization in arid regions. Fossil salts can be dissolved under water storage or water transmission structures

causing salinization (Bresler et al., 1982). The ingress of seawater along the coast surges salt contents in coastal areas (Rao et al., 2014). The salt loaded winds and rains (sea sprays) along sea coasts carry oceanic salts along with them in sufficient amount to cause salinization in coastal regions. The coastal regions are also exposed to the risk of progressive salinization of land due to natural disasters such as storms, cyclones, tidal surges, flooding etc.

Secondary salinization: (Anthropogenic activities of soil salinization):

Secondary salinization has been salinized by man-made causing factors. Mainly as a consequence of land clearing for cultivation, inappropriate irrigation, canal water seepage, overdosing of agrochemicals and use of waste effluents. Change of land use from natural forest vegetation to annual food crops decreases evapotranspiration and increases leaching. The presence of less permeable subsoil layers may intercept the percolating water passing through saline sediments resulting in lateral seepage, causing salinization in low lying areas (Doering and Sandoval, 1976).

Inappropriate use of brackish and saline irrigation water, poor drainage conditions, rising water tables etc., lead to secondary salinization of land and water resources (Rao et al., 2014). Recently, wide range of 310 million hectares (ha) area is irrigated, out of which 20–33% area is estimated to be affected by salt (Glick et al., 2007; Jamil et al., 2011; Shahid et al., 2018). Over extraction of groundwater transports salts to soil surface where they get precipitated when water evaporizes (Rao et al., 2014). Water logging and soil salinization in the Indira Gandhi Nahar Priyojna (IGNP) in India is an example of canal water seepage. Around 50% of the command area of IGNP has observed water logging area (Tewari et al., 1997). Use of untreated sewage effluent, dumping of industrial outlet onto the soil and water etc. may also cause the entry of heavy metals into soils.

The soil salinization has remarkable environmental, ecological, agricultural, and social impacts in terms of decreasing agricultural lands, low agricultural productivity, uncertain and unstable livelihood security, low economic returns, and poor quality of life. Excess salts effects the metabolism of soil flora and fauna, leading ultimately to the destruction of all soil life, altering fertile and productive lands into barren and desert lands. Soils are rendered useless agriculturally as well as for several other purposes like e.g., construction work.

Ecological effects:

Salinity of soil primarily affects ecological soil functions. The adverse impact of increased Electric conductivity (EC) on important soil processes like respiration, residue decomposition, nitrification, and de-nitrification through the decrease of soil biodiversity and microorganism activity is well known (Singh, 2015). Depending on its form and stage, soil salinity degrades fertile and productive land and reducing all vegetation (Chesworth, 2008; Jones et al., 2012; Trnka et al., 2013). Saline soils enter a negative feedback of Organic Carbon (OC) loss as decreased fertility and microbial and enzyme activities (Singh, 2015) leads to less biomass production which is badly effects distribution and stability of soil aggregates (Six et al., 2000) and promotes a higher portion of plant input in the accumulated organic matter. These changes increase distribution of clay particles and greater wind and water erosion rates (Paix et al., 2013) that further intensify OC losses. Regarding Carbon, there is currently limited evidence on the Carbon stock trends in salt affected soil, whereas Carbon dynamics studies are contradictory (Wong et al., 2010). As a feedback of its effects on ecological functions, salinization impacts a series of environmental interactions thus undermining water infiltration and storage capacity of soil water resulting in increased water runoff and erosion.

Socio-economic effects

Although salinization has strong implications on socio-economic aspects, yet very few publications are presented in literature (Shahid et al., 2018). Social consequences of soil salinization include decline in agricultural harvest, low income, change of livelihood preferences

and related social limits. The estimates show that the global annual cost of salt affected land degradation in irrigated areas could be US\$ 27.3 billion in terms of lost crop production (Qadir et al., 2014).

The estimates based on 2012–14 average data suggested that, due to soil salinization in India loses annually 16.84 million tons of farm production (crops such as cereals, oilseeds, pulses) valued at Rs. 230.20 billion (Mandal et al., 2018). It has strong implications on the national economy. The Uttar Pradesh state is topped the list with 7.69 million tons production loss, followed by Gujarat state with 4.83 million tons production loss. Gujarat and Uttar Pradesh have the largest salinized area (>50% of cultivated area) in the country. These two states only share around 79% monetary losses in the country.

Peoples' living standard, regular life activities and socio-economic conditions are poorly affected. Farmers in response to salinity problem are forced to shift their livelihood strategies (Ziaul Haider and Zaber Hossain, 2013) in coastal regions. Farmers in saline regions are generally resource inhibited and required financial and technical assistance to sustain their livelihood efforts (Oo et al., 2013).

Salinity effects on plant growth

Plants commonly face environmental conditions e.g. abiotic stress such as drought, chilling, freezing, high temperatures and higher salinity of soils which can delay growth and development, reduce productivity, and, in extreme cases cause plant death (Krasensky and Jonak, 2012). Salinity affects almost all aspects of plant progress including germination, vegetative growth, and reproductive improvement (Machado and Serralheiro et al., 2017). Stress condition plants in saline environments experiences two types of stress, the osmotic stress and nutrient stress. Low osmotic potential of water in saline soils which adversely affects water absorption by plants is called as osmotic stress. Nutrient stress is a process of both 1) specific ion toxicity (sodium (Na), chloride (Cl), Boron (B) etc.) and 2) insufficiency of plant nutrients (N, K, P, Ca, Fe, Zn). It also results in nutritional imbalances (Munns and Tester, 2008). Salinity of soil significantly decreases phosphorus uptake by plants because phosphate ions precipitate with Ca ions (Bano and Fatima, 2009). The supplemented sodium (Na⁺) absorption in sodic soils reduces K⁺ absorption which poorly affects the enzymatic activities involved in metabolic processes like photosynthesis and protein synthesis (Hauser and Horie, 2010), which is damaging for plant growth (Katiyar-Agarwal et al., 2005).

Increased salinity is a severe problem and a foremost limiting factor for crop production around the globe (Wahid et al., 2007). Reduced leaf area, chlorophyll content and stomatal conductance in saline soils also affects photosynthesis. Salinity affects photosynthesis by decreasing CO₂ availability as a result of diffusion limitations and a reduction of the contents of photosynthetic pigments capacity of the plant through reduced leaf growth and inhibited photosynthesis, limiting its ability to grow (Netondo et al., 2004, Hauser and Horie, 2010). e.g. Salt accumulation in spinach inhibits photosynthesis, primarily by decreasing stomatal and mesophyll conductances to CO₂ and reducing chlorophyll content, which can affect light absorbance. Apart from high nutrient deficiencies and toxicities, other restrictions for plant growth in saline-sodic soils includes physically poor soil conditions, viz. low water and air permeability, high runoff, low water holding capacity (WHC), surface crusting, and hard setting. They effects plant root penetration, seedling, and tillage operations (Murtaza et al., 2006).

The salt stresses disturb acutely to the plant morphology, functioning and homeostasis and decrease the plant biomass (Parvaiz et al., 2014). High stages of soil salinity can significantly inhibit seed germination and seedling growth Influence of Salinity on seed germination of many crops by creating an osmotic potential outside the seed inhibiting the absorption of water, or by the toxic effect of Sodium (Na⁺) and Chloride (Cl⁻) (Khajeh-Hosseini et al., 2003). Salt tolerance of the plants may vary according to the environmental conditions of plant and its growth stages. The excess amount of Sodium (Na⁺) and

Chloride (Cl⁻) in the protoplasm show disturbance in the ionic balance and also show the ion-specific effects on enzyme proteins and membranes. Several researchers have reported plant growth reduction as a result of salinity stress, e.g. in onion (Chaudhry et al., 2020) tomato (RomeroAranda et al., 2001), cotton (Meloni et al., 2001) and sugar beet (Ghoulam et al., 2002) and many more vegetables. However, there are changes in tolerance to salinity among species and cultivars as well as among the different plant growth parameters recorded. Shrivastava P. et al., 2014 presented review on the enhancement of productivity under stressed conditions and increased resistance of plants against salinity by application of plant growth promoting microorganisms.

Restoration measures in agriculture

Saline lands can be converted to more productive crop lands by preventing the influx of saline water through proper farm management practices, correcting soil toxicities, nutrient deficiencies, and leaching the salts out of the root zone. The reclamation and management practices costs can be reduced by growing salt tolerant vegetation. These practices are discussed below.

Farm management practices

Salinity can be controlled by changing in farm management practices. Munns et al.2002 proposes that irrigated agriculture could be sustained by better irrigation practices such as adoption of partial root zone drying methodology, and drip or micro jet irrigation to optimize use of water. They suggested that salinity could also be contained by reducing the amount of water passing beyond the roots by reintroducing deep rooted perennial plants that continue to grow and use water during the seasons but it's not supports annual crop plants. This may restore the balance between rainfall and water use, thus preventing the movement of salt to the soil surface. Singh et al., 2003 reported the chemical amendment based technology has been developed to reclaim salt affected soils. By adopting this technology about 1.3 million hector (ha) area has been reclaimed in the states of Haryana, Punjab and Western Uttar Pradesh (Singh et al., 2007)

Leaching

Leaching soils to remove soluble salts is the most effective method known to reclamation of saline soils. This requires good permeability of the soil and good quality irrigation water. Removal of salts by leaching reduces soluble salt from the root zone, especially in shallow rooted crops but might cause permeability to decrease and pH to increase resulting in decomposition of roots as soil is changed from saline sodic to sodic (Dregne, 1976). Although the best long term solution to salinization is to provide adequate drainage, this process is costly (Toenniessen, 1984). The process of leaching was successful in the depth of 0-10 cm (Mahendran 2007).

The other management technologies use such as salt tolerant varieties in crops, use of mulch application, foliar application of fertilizers, fertilizer management as well as nutrient management, green manure and green leaf manure.

Uses of salt stress tolerant plants

According to United Nations Environment Program, about 20% of the agriculture land and 50% cropland around the world face salinity problems. The caloric and nutritional possibilities of agriculture outcome are limited by salt stress conditions of land (Deveshi Patel et al., 2020). Some areas have naturally occurring salinity and salt stress tolerant plants may provide a better or perhaps the only means of utilizing these resources for food production. Using of salt tolerance varieties in the efficient ways to solve the problem of soil salinity. Salinity can possibly also be managed through biologically manipulating the plants (Shannon, 1984). Great effort is, therefore, being directed toward the development of salt tolerant crop genotypes through the use of plant breeding strategies involving the introgression of the genetic background from salt tolerant wild species into cultivated plants (Shannon, 1984; Pitman and Läuchli, 2002). However, it should be borne in mind that there is also the risk that the availability of salt tolerant genotypes will result in less effort

to recover saline areas or to prevent salinization. In the longer term this will be counterproductive.

Salt tolerance in crops will also allow the more effective use of poor quality irrigation water. (Niknam and McComb 2000) suggested that trees could be planted to take up some of the excess salt since they have high water use and can lower water tables to decrease salt discharge into streams and prevent secondary salinization of the surrounding areas.

Organic and Microbial Remediation

Application of organic amendments, such as livestock manures and composts, increases the soil organic carbon concentration and improves the soil's macro-aggregation processes and structure formation. These processes improve soil permeability, increasing the leaching capacity of salts from the rhizosphere, and simultaneously decrease evaporation rates, reducing salt accumulation in the surface soil layer (Lakhdar et al., 2009). In addition to livestock-derived organic amendments, this practice can also utilize waste materials, such as municipal solid wastes, transforming these environmental burdens into highly valorized resources (Lakhdar et al., 2009). Yet, special attention should be paid when using highly-saline solid wastes (or manures), which their application may aggravate soil salinity.

Conclusion: -

The worldwide increasing salinization of arable land renders salinity one of the most harmful threats to modern agriculture and challenging food production and security in India. It is a dynamic process caused by several natural and anthropogenic processes, and quite often, the socio economic and political considerations become extremely important in speeding up the processes of soil salinization. Sometimes, such factors are beyond the control of individual farmers. Several on farm tested technologies are available for the reclamation and management of salt affected soils. The efforts put in by government agencies and farmers for the reclamation and restoration of saline soils in the country so far have been encouraging. Judicious selection of sites for the establishment of croplands, alongside with the use of water-saving irrigation technologies, can reduce the risk of waterlogging and soil salinization processes. In saline soils, routine measures should be taken to allow effective drainage of excess water, alongside with flushing and leaching of salts. Further, the use of conservation agricultural practices, such as crop residue management, manuring/composting, nutrient management and proper crop selection can considerably reduce the risk of soil salinity.

References: -

1. **Aquastat, (2016).** FAO's Information System on Water and Agriculture [WWW Document].
2. **Bano, A., and Fatima, M. (2009).** Salt tolerance in Zea mays (L.) following inoculation with Rhizobium and Pseudomonas. *Biol. Ferti. Soils.* 45, 405–413.
3. **Berendse, F., van Ruijven, J., Jongejans, E., Keesstra, S., (2015).** Loss of plant species diversity reduces soil erosion resistance. *Ecosystems* 18, 881–888. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10021-015-9869-6>
4. **Bhattacharyya, R., Ghosh, B. N., Mishra, P. K., Mandal, B., Rao, C. S., Sarkar, D., et al. (2015).** Soil degradation in India: Challenges and potential solutions. *Sustainability* 7, 3528–3570. doi: 10.3390/su7043528
5. **Bresler, E., McNeal, B. L., and Carter, D. L. (1982).** *Saline and Sodic Soils: Principles-Dynamics-Modeling.* New York, NY: Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, 227.
6. **Brevik, E., Cerdà, A., Mataix-Solera, J., Pereg, L., Quinton, J., Six, J., Van Oost, K., (2015).** The interdisciplinary nature of SOIL. *Soil* 1, 117–129. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-117-2015>.
7. Chesworth, W., (2008). *Encyclopedia of Soil Science.* Encyclopedia of Earth Sciences Series Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-3995-9>

8. **D.K.Sharma and Anshumansingh et al.,(2015)**. Salinity research in India- Achievements, Challenges and Future Prospects. *Water and energy international* pp 35.
9. **Dabral, P. P. et al., (2008)**. Soil erosion assessment in a hilly catchment of North Eastern India using USLE, GIS and remote sensing. *Water Resources Management*, 22: 1783-1798
10. **Decock, C., Lee, J., Necpalova, M., Pereira, E.I.P., Tendall, D.M., Six, J., (2015)**. Mitigating N₂O emissions from soil: from patching leaks to transformative action. *Soil* 1, 687–694. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-687-2015>
11. **Devarshi Patel, Swati Jayswal, Hitesh Solanki and Bharat Maitreya., (2020)**. Effect of Salinity On Different Vegetable Crops-A Review. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research* Vol. 11, Issue, 02 (C), pp. 37418-37422. DOI: 10.24327/IJRSR
12. **Doering, E. J., and Sandoval, F. M. (1976)**. Hydrology of saline seeps in the Northern Great Plains. *Trans. ASEA*. 19, 856–861. doi: 10.13031/2013.36134
13. **Dregne, H.E., (1976)**. Soils of arid regions. Elsevier Scientific Publishing Company, Amsterdam.
14. **Escobar, J. C. et al., (2009)**. Biofuels: environment, technology and food security. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 13(6), 1275-1287.
15. **FAO, (2011)**. The State of the World's Land and Water Resources for Food and Agriculture: Managing Systems at Risk. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
16. **Foley, J. A., Defries, R., Asner, G. P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S. R., et al. (2005)**. Global consequences of land use. *Science* 309, 570–574. doi: 10.1126/science.1111772
17. **G.GururajaRao, A.D.Kanani, DevshreePurohit and DivyangWaghela et al.,(2019)**. Coastal saline soils of Gujarat (India): Problems, Reclamation measures and management strategies. *Research Developments in Saline Agriculture*, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5832-6_21
18. **Ghassemi, F., Jakeman, A.J., Nix, H.A., et al., (1995)**. Salinisation of Land and Water Resources: Human Causes, Extent, Management and Case Studies. CAB international, Wallingford, UK.
19. **Ghoulam, C., Foursy, A. & Fares, K., (2002)**. Effects of salt stress on growth, inorganic ions and proline accumulation in relation to osmotic adjustment in five sugar beet cultivars. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 47, 39-50.
20. **Glick, B. R., Cheng, Z., Czarny, J., and Duan, J. (2007)**. Promotion of plant growth by ACC deaminase producing soil bacteria. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 119, 329–339. doi: 10.1007/s10658-007-9162-4
21. **Godfray, H. C. J., Beddington, J. R., Crute, I. R., Haddad, L., Lawrence, D., Muir, J. F., et al. (2010)**. Food security: the challenge of feeding 9 billion people. *Science* 327, 812–818. doi: 10.1126/science.1185383
22. **Hauser, F., and Horie, T. (2010)**. A conserved primary salt tolerance mechanism mediated by HKT transporters: a mechanism for sodium exclusion and maintenance of high K⁺/Na⁺ ratio in leaves during salinity stress. *Plant Cell Environ.* 33, 552–565. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3040.2009.02056.x
23. **Jamil, A., Riaz, S., Ashraf, M., and Foolad, M.R. (2011)**. Gene expression profiling of plants under salt stress. *Crit. Rev. Plant*
24. **Jones, A., Panagos, P., Barcelo, S., Bouraoui, F., Bosco, C., Dewitte, O., Gardi, C., Hervás, J., Hiederer, R., Jeffery, S., Montanarella, L., Penizek, V., Tóth, G., Van Den Eeckhaut, M., Liedekerke, M.V., Verheijen, F., Yigini, Y., (2012)**. The State of Soil in Europe-A Contribution of the JRC to the European Environment Agency's Environment State and Out-look Report–SOER 2010. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg <http://dx.doi.org/10.2788/77361>
25. **Julia Krasensky, Claudia Jonak.(2012)**. Drought salt, and temperature stress-induced metabolic rearrangement and regulatory networks. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 63(4):1593–608. DOI: 10.1093/jxb/err460
26. **Katiyar-Agarwal, S., Verslues, P., and Zhu, J. K. (2005)**. "Plant nutrition for food security, human health and environmental protection," in *Mechanisms of Salt Tolerance in Plants*, eds C. J. Li et al., (Beijing: Tsinghua University Press) 44–45.
27. **Keesstra, S., Geissen, V., Mosse, K., Piirainen, S., Scudiero, E., Leistra, M., van Schaik, L., (2012)**. Soil as a filter for groundwater quality. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 4, 507– 516. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2012.10.007>
28. **Khajeh-Hosseini M., Powell A. A., Bingham I. J. (2003)**. The interaction between salinity stress and seed vigor during germination of soybean seeds. *Seed Sci. Technol.* 31:715-725.
29. **Lakhdar, A., Rabhi, M., Ghnaya, T., Montemurro, F., Jedidi, N., and Abdelly, C. (2009)**. Effectiveness of Compost Use in Salt-Affected Soil. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 171, 29–37. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.05.132.
30. **Lotze-Campen, H., et al. (2008)**. Global food demand, productivity growth, and the scarcity of land and water resources: a spatially explicit mathematical programming approach. *Agricultural Economics*, 39: 325-338.
31. **Machado, R. M. A., and Serralheiro, R. P. (2017)**. Soil salinity: effect on vegetable crop growth. management practices to prevent and mitigate soil salinization. *Horticulturae* 3:30. doi: 10.3390/horticulturae3020030
32. **Mahendran, S. (2007)**. Technology development for saline water irrigation to increase the crop production in the coastal saline soils of Ramanathapuram district. CSRC. TNAU.
33. **Mandal, S., Raju, R., Kumar, A., Kumar, P., and Sharma, P. C. (2018)**. Current status of research, technology response and policy needs of salt-affected soils in India – a review. *Ind. Soc. Coastal Agri. Res.* 36, 40–53
34. **Meloni, D.A., Oliva, M.A., Ruiz, H.A. & Martinez, C.A., (2001)**. Contribution of proline and inorganic solutes to osmotic adjustment in cotton under salt stress. *J. Plant Nutr.* 24, 599-612.
35. **Minhas, P. S. (1998a)**. Leaching for salinity control. In: *Agricultural Salinity Management in India*. N. K. Tyagi and P. S. Minhas (Eds.), Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal. pp. 161-174.
36. **Minhas, P. S. (1998b)**. Crop production in saline soils. In: *Agricultural Salinity Management in India*. N. K. Tyagi and P. S. Minhas (Eds.), Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal. pp. 325-350.
37. **Minhas, P. S., and Sharma, O. P. (2003)**. Management of soil salinity and alkalinity problems in India. *J. Crop Prod.* 7, 181–230. doi: 10.1300/J144v07n01_07
38. **Minhas, P. S., and Sharma, O. P. (2003)**. Management of soil salinity and alkalinity problems in India. *J. Crop Prod.* 7, 181–230. doi: 10.1300/J144v07n01_07
39. **Munns R, Tester M. (2008)**. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.*, 59: 651-681.
40. **Munns, R., (2002)**. Comparative physiology of salt and water stress. *Plant Cell Environ.* 25, 239-250.
41. **Niknam, S.R. & Mccomb, J., (2000)**. Salt tolerance screening of selected Australian woody species – a review. *Forest Ecol. and Manage.* 139, 1-19.

42. **Nosetto, M. D. et al., (2007).** The effects of tree establishment on water and salt dynamics in naturally salt affected grasslands. *Oecologia*, 152: 695-705.
43. **Oldeman, L. R. (1998).** Soil degradation: a threat to food security. International Soil Reference and Information Centre. Wageningen.
44. **Oo, A. N., Iwai, C. B., and Saenjan, P. (2013).** Food security and socio-economic impacts of soil salinization in northeast Thailand. *Inter. J. Environ. Rural Dev.* 4, 76–81.
45. **Paix, M., Lanhai, L., Xi, C., Varenyam, A., Nyongesah, M., Habiyaremye, G., (2013).** Physico-chemical properties of saline soils and aeolian dust. *L. Degrad. Dev.* 24, 539–547. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ldr.1148>
46. **Pardeep Kumar and Pardeep K sharma et al., (2020).** Soil salinity and food security in India. *Frontier in sustainable food systems.* doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2020.533781
47. **Parfitt, J. et al., (2010).** Food waste within food supply chains: quantification and potential for change to 2050. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 365: 3065-3081.
48. **Parry, M., et al. (1999).** Climate change and world food security: a new assessment. *Global Environmental Change*, 9: 51-67.
49. **Parvaiz M. (2014).** Response of Maize to salt stress a critical review. *International Journal of Healthcare Sciences (IJHS)* 1(1): 13-25
50. **Pimentel, D. (2006).** Soil erosion: a food and environmental threat. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 8: 119-137.
51. **Pitman, M.G. & Lauchli, A., (2002).** Global impact of salinity and agricultural ecosystems. In: A. Lauchli and U. Lüttge (eds.), *Salinity: environment-plants molecules*. Kluwer, Dordrecht, pp. 3-20.